

Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of 7-Benzodiazepinyl-, 7-Pyrazolyl- and 7-Isoxazolyl-1,2-benzisoxazoles

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Synthesis of a few 1-[7'-(3'-methyl/ethyl)-6'-hydroxy-1',2'-benzisoxazolyl]-3-(substituted-phenyl)-propane-1,3-diones is described. By the action of *o*-phenylenediamine, hydrazine and hydroxylamine on these 1,3-diones, 7-benzodiazepinyl-, 7-pyrazolyl- and 7-isoxazolyl-1,2-benzisoxazoles, respectively were obtained. Antifungal activity of most of these compounds is described.

β -DIKETONES exhibit various activities, like tuberculostatic, bacteriostatic¹ etc. Introduction of 1,2-benzisoxazolyl group may modify the activity of these diketones. A few β -diketones having benzisoxazolyl nucleus as one of the substituents have been reported^{2,3}. In the present study, β -diketones were prepared by esterifying 3-methyl/ethyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetyl-1,2-benzisoxazole by adopting Marathay's procedure⁴ 1 and subsequent Baker-Venkatraman transformation of the esters formed 2.

1,2-Benzisoxazole nucleus exhibits various activities like tuberculostatic⁵, antidepressant⁶, antibacterial⁷ etc. It is very likely that introduction of different heterocyclic nuclei, like benzodiazepinyl, pyrazolyl, isoxazolyl etc. may modify the activity of the parent nucleus. Thus, the reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine with β -diketones (2) was carried out by a procedure described by Thiele and Stemming⁸ to obtain compounds 3. These compounds can exist in either 3a or 3b form. The nmr spectra of the compounds showed a singlet around δ 4.4 with an integrated ratio of 1-proton, confirming the structure of the compounds as 3a. The reaction of hydrazine was carried out in neutral medium on the β -diketones (2) to obtain either 4a and/or 4d. Since tlc of these compounds showed a single spot in each case, it can be either 4a or 4b. Condensation of hydroxylamine with β -diketones (2) in neutral medium lead to the formation of either 5a and/or 5b. Tlc of these compounds showed a single spot in each case, it can be either 5a or 5b.

All these reactions are described in Scheme 1.

Experimental

All the m.ps. were taken in an open capillary and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (nujol) were scanned on a Beckmann 137 spectrophotometer.

The nmr spectra were recorded on 100 MHz and 60 MHz spectrophotometers with TMS as an internal standard.

1-[7'-(3'-Ethyl-6'-hydroxy-1',2'-benzisoxazolyl)]-3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-propane-1,3-dione: To a solution of 1⁴ (0.01 mol) in anhydrous pyridine was added powdered KOH (0.03 mol). The mixture was stirred for 30 min and kept at room temperature overnight. The solid was isolated by pouring the reaction mixture in concentrated HCl and ice, and crystallised from EtOH - AcOH to yield the product (78%), m.p. 175°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1600 (C=O), 1500 (C=N), 1220 (C-O-N) and 820 cm⁻¹ (benzisoxazole-ring stretch); δ (CDCl₃) 1.5 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.0 (2H, q, CH₂), 3.3 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.2 (2H, s, COCH₂CO) and 7.0-8.3 (6H, m, Ar-H).

3-Methyl-6-hydroxy-7-[4'-2'-(2"-thienyl)-1',5'-benzodiazepinyl]-1,2-benzisoxazole: A mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine and β -diketone (2) in 1:1 molar ratio was refluxed in presence of ethanol and acetic acid for 4-6 h. After cooling, the mixture deposited a solid which was filtered, washed with ethanol, dried and crystallised from ethanol to yield the product (88%), m.p. 222°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3100 (N-H) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.64 (3H, s, CH₃-benzisoxazole), 4.44 (CH-benzodiazepine), 4.9 (1H, s, N-H-benzodiazepine) and 6.94-8.15 (9H, m, Ar-H). Rest of the compounds were prepared in a similar fashion.

3-Ethyl-6-hydroxy-[7-(3' (or 5'),-5' (or 3')-(2"-thienyl)-pyrazolyl]-1,2-benzisoxazole: A mixture of β -diketone (2) and hydrazine hydrate (80%) in 1:1.5 molar ratio in methanol was refluxed for 2-4 h. The contents of the flask after cooling, deposited a solid which was washed with ethanol and dried, and crystallisation from ethanol yield the product (51%), m.p. 243°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3200 (N-H) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (TFA) 1.53 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.1 (2H, q, CH₂) and 6.9-7.6 (6H, m, Ar 5HS+pyrazole-H). Rest of the compounds were prepared in a similar fashion.

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Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS**

Sl. no.	Substituent		Compd. 1		Compd. 2		Compd. 3a		Compd. 4a/4b		Compd. 5a/5b	
	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	M.p. °C	Yield %						
1.	OH ₂	<i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl	152	52	154	71	193 ^c	66	245	40	210	81
2.	OH ₂	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl	159	46	175 ^c	75*	216 ^c	98	248	67	280	20
3.	OH ₂	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -phenyl	145	48	101	77	193	98	195	89	—	—
4.	OH ₂	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ -phenyl	193	42	160 ^d	94	170 ^c	41	227 ^c	83	258	50
5.	OH ₂	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl	157	51	174 ^c	76*	220	58	—	—	275	50
6.	OH ₂	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	168	59	203 ^c	74*	225 ^c	98	—	—	250	40
7.	OH ₂	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	178	54	216 ^d	77	195 ^c	83	—	—	210	40
8.	OH ₂	2''-Furyl	122	60	180 ^d	89	—	—	187	47	218	81
9.	OH ₂	2''-Thienyl	150	58	160	76	222	89	263	61	210	84
10.	OH ₂	Phenyl	—	—	137	70*	220	32	171	41	192	51
11.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl	198	50	120 ^b	66	151	75	175	81	213	90
12.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl	110 ^b	54	126	88*	175	91	194	51	210	81
13.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -phenyl	105	56	94	89	170	82	140	69	205	78
14.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ -phenyl	120	57	110	68	140	82	200 ^a	99	—	—
15.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl	121	57	175	78	197	91	190	91	—	—
16.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl	124	56	107 ^c	78*	162 ^c	83	—	—	—	—
17.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	116	53	180	66	194 ^c	92	—	—	—	—
18.	C ₆ H ₅	2''-Furyl	105	58	154	69*	193 ^c	83	241	61	170	91
19.	C ₆ H ₅	2''-Thienyl	118	56	137	83*	180 ^c	76	243	57	—	—
20.	C ₆ H ₅	Phenyl	—	—	119 ^b	52*	140	82	125 ^b	81	169	51

Crystallised from ^aMeOH, ^bAqueous EtOH, ^cEtOH + AcOH, ^dAcOH, and the rest from EtOH.

* Refs. 2 and 3.

** All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Substituent		Compd. 2			Compd. 3a			Compd. 4a/4b			Compd. 5a/5b								
	R	R'	Zone of inhibition in mm			At 25 ppm			At 50 ppm			At 25 ppm								
			A.b.	H.m.	P.a.	A.b.	H.m.	P.a.	A.b.	H.m.	P.a.	A.b.	H.m.	P.a.						
1.	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl	14	10	16	5	9	10	80	20	35	—	—	—	20	20	34	28	30	30
2.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl	9	12	15	7	5	0	21	38	29	—	—	—	80	33	21	—	—	—
3.	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -phenyl	—	—	—	10	9	15	20	40	31	37	29	88	20	30	18	—	—	—
4.	CH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ -phenyl	19	30	22	30	20	35	19	31	20	—	—	—	20	22	35	—	—	—
5.	CH ₃	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	—	—	—	26	40	38	16	20	15	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
6.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	—	—	—	0	0	0	40	25	87	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
7.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl	—	—	—	28	37	30	36	40	27	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
8.	CH ₃	2''-Thienyl	—	—	—	25	29	20	28	28	84	—	—	—	25	30	40	20	36	25
9.	CH ₃	2''-Furyl	20	28	19	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	20	25	30	19	31	27
10.	CH ₃	Phenyl	—	—	—	39	36	40	49	31	25	—	—	—	32	30	35	27	34	38
11.	C ₂ H ₅	<i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl	34	30	26	34	40	30	34	28	40	35	25	88	—	—	—	42	38	30
12.	C ₂ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl	40	15	31	0	0	0	25	10	8	80	25	36	—	—	—	35	20	24
13.	C ₂ H ₅	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -phenyl	29	26	24	9	15	21	28	20	36	32	30	35	—	—	—	40	29	21
14.	C ₂ H ₅	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ -phenyl	—	—	—	35	35	31	32	30	35	40	45	42	—	—	—	—	—	—
15.	C ₂ H ₅	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	—	—	—	17	4	0	0	16	12	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
16.	C ₂ H ₅	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	—	—	—	36	30	40	40	26	30	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
17.	C ₂ H ₅	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl	—	—	—	37	29	38	20	30	18	20	27	38	—	—	—	—	—	—
18.	C ₂ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl	44	10	17	30	30	41	0	0	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
19.	C ₂ H ₅	2''-Thienyl	31	33	41	38	40	30	28	37	29	45	25	41	—	—	—	—	—	—
20.	C ₂ H ₅	2''-Furyl	38	18	28	—	—	—	—	—	—	35	25	44	—	—	—	23	40	41
21.	C ₂ H ₅	Phenyl	—	—	—	40	37	36	42	33	40	—	—	—	37	19	21	28	29	39

Chloroform No. inhibition

* A.b. = *Alternaria brassicae*, H.m. = *Helminthosporium maydis*, P.a. = *Pestotia annonicola*.

3-Ethyl-6-hydroxy-[7-3' (or 5'), 5' (or 3')-(*o*-toluyl)-isoxazolyl]-1,2-benzisoxazole : A mixture of β -diketone (2) and hydroxylamine in 1 : 1.5 molar ratio in methanol was refluxed for 4-6 h. The reaction mixture after cooling, deposited a solid which was filtered washed with water, dried, and crystallised from ethanol to yield the product (61%), m.p. 140°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3200 (NH) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (TFA) 1.53 (3H, t, CH₃ of benzisoxazole), 2.56 (3H, s, CH₃-Ar) and 7.0-9.3 (7H, m, aromatic+isoxazole CH). Rest of the compounds were prepared in the similar fashion. The physical data of all the compounds are presented Table 1.

Antifungal activity : About 55 compounds were tested for antifungal activity at 25 and 50 ppm. At 100 ppm the compounds developed toxicity to the fungi. By adopting the paper disc method* and using glucose nitrate medium, compounds were tested against three pathogenic fungi, namely *Helminthosporium maydis*, *Alternaria brassicae* and *Pestotia annonicola*. The activity results are given in Table 2. In majority of the compounds, it was observed that the activity was more when R is C₂H₅ than when R is CH₃. Similarly, the activity was more when R' is thienyl, *p*-OCH₃-phenyl, phenyl, toluyl than when R' is nitrophenyl and chlorophenyl. In some cases, compounds 2 (6),

2 (12) and 3 (18), the fungal growth was found to be normal.

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